

Abstract:

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G.J. Schmitz: A Flowchart Scheme for Information Retrieval in ICME Settings
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“A Flow-Chart Scheme for Information Retrieval in ICME settings”

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Interoperability between models implies the need for the definition of a flow of information or a “workflow” and also the specification of timing between the different operations of the different models acting on a state or on subsets of a state description. Getting such workflows eventually well-defined, operational and also extendable to future decision making processes needs some structural considerations. An instructive approach is seen in the specification of workflows for decision making in different areas, where different types of flowchart tools are needed and used to control and steer the workflow.

The proposed flowchart scenario is based on the description of a system state and its evolution being influenced by all types of phenomena occurring at all scales. The system state further defines the properties which can be extracted from the system state information.

Different types of models/tools operate on this state and a generic classification is proposed being based on the character/functionality of the physics equation like (i) Evolution equations, (ii) Property equations, (iii) Balance equations, and (iv) conservation equations.

Evolution models –EVOLVERS - under given conditions turn the actual state or at least parts of the actual state into a new state at a later instant of time. Such models accordingly change the state. Evolution models are characterized by any type of time dependency within the physics equation or within the materials relations. Any EVOLVER needs the specification of an initial state which can e.g. be generated synthetically by CREATOR type tools.

Models and tools acting on an existing state to extract desired properties are called EXTRACTORS. These „post-processing“-type models/tools *do not* alter the state and thus can operate in parallel to EVOLVERS. Balance type equations allow describing aspects of the equilibrium state thus providing criteria e.g. for the termination of EVOLVERS.

Eventually, to allow informatics type workflows these models, states and post-processors have to be complemented by further tools like INPUT/OUTPUT and especially by DECISIONS allowing steering the workflow. The presentation will provide first examples of flowcharts being applied to information retrieval in ICME settings.

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